

Guidance on the completion of this tool

Section 1 – Baseline Observations

- Fill in the baseline observations for when the individual is well.
- If some of these are difficult to obtain, state the last date that they were obtained.
- Within the box 'Important individual information' add individual things of note, see examples:
 - This individual will only tolerate a particular thermometer
 - This individual will not tolerate blood pressure being checked
 - This individual is very unwell if they do tolerate blood pressure being checked
 - This individual's temperature may not increase when an infection is present

Section 2 – Historical/Common signs of Physical Pain

- List previous and current signs of physical pain that can be recognised in this individual, see examples to reflect upon:
 - What does the individual do?
 - How do they present?
 - What do they sound like?
- Photo visual of pain – Attach a photo of the person to the front of the tool, only if this will assist in the recognition of a pain expression for this individual.

Section 3 – Pain Severity

- State whether the individual will react or present differently depending on the severity of their pain or not.
- List signs of pain intensity levels for that individual, reflect upon the following:
 - Does this individual's pain behaviour change or intensify as their pain intensifies?
 - Can the individual express the intensity of their pain? If so, how?

Section 4 – Historical/Common causes of Physical Pain

- List previous or current conditions that cause the individual pain, see examples:
 - Urinary tract infections
 - Chest infections
 - Skin issues
- This list is not exhaustive, but acts a guide to the initial assessment of the cause of the individual's pain.

Section 5 – Historically Successful Interventions

- List individual interventions for relief of the person's pain, see examples:
 - Administer analgesia – see PRN guidelines
 - Reposition
 - Complete a urinalysis

Section 6 – Historical/common signs of Emotional/Social/Spiritual Pain/Distress

- State whether this individual's signs of these facets of pain will differ from those that indicate physical pain.
- See examples to reflect upon:
 - What does the individual do?
 - How do they present?
 - What do they sound like?

Section 7 – Historical/Common causes of Emotional/Social/Spiritual Pain/Distress

- List previous or current causes of emotional/social/spiritual pain/distress for this individual, see examples:
 - Missing family/grieving
 - Not attending their day service

Section 8 – Historically Successful Interventions

- Reflect upon the interventions that will assist with the relief of this individual's distress, see examples:
 - Video calling a family member
 - One to one time with someone
 - A warm bath

Section 9 – Additional Individual Things of Relevance to Note

- Add anything that may be a beneficial addition to the information on the document for this individual.

Tool to be reviewed yearly and updated as needed